

Methods of working with problem in elementary school mathematics

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Abstract:

The article focuses on how to learn problem-solving and independent reading in elementary school math lessons, how to learn problem-solving, and how to read it independently.

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Introduction

Problem solving is an important component of math education. It is unthinkable to master mathematics without solving the problem. Solving problems in mathematics is a natural way to put theory into practice (Baxtishodovich, Suyunovich, News, & 2017, n.d.; Turner & Freiermuth, 2017).

In the process of mastering one or another of the theoretical material studied in the elementary grades, the solution of the issues plays an important role. The program states: "The arithmetic of natural numbers and the study of zero are based on a system of practical tasks and practical tasks. This means that every new concept of content is always associated with solving a problem that requires its application, which helps explain the meaning of this concept (Razakov Sh & Shakhgunova, 2001)."

Students are introduced to mathematical relationships by teaching them how to solve problems. There are two types of issues that are usually solved: simple and complex. Issues that require only one action to be resolved are simple issues. Issues that require several interrelated actions to resolve are complex. Simple questions provide the basis for students to build the knowledge, skills and abilities needed to solve complex problems. Simple and complex issues can be used to improve knowledge, to strengthen and to perfect the acquired knowledge. Problems are a useful tool for developing children's thinking skills and usually contain confidential information. The search for this information requires the problem solver to independently analyze and

synthesize, compare facts, and summarize. Teaching these ways of learning is one of the important purposes of teaching mathematics (Anonymous, 2010; Blasko, Electronics, & 1997, n.d.).

Teaching students how to solve problems independently allows the teacher to use the resources available to students in their mental abilities. This is another important function of the issues. When dealing with problems develops an interest in the subject, develops independence, freedom, demand, diligence, and purpose. Students are taught various elements of discipline by teaching them how to solve problems. The questions help to broaden students' minds, familiarize them with the life of the person, the village, the industrial and agricultural labor.

Different ways of solving problems are also important. Children need to learn how to apply the knowledge they acquire on the properties of arithmetic operations to solving problems. It is important to note that the program should help students identify the most feasible ways to address a particular problem and select the smallest of them in a clear and reasonable manner. In addition to solving ready-to-use issues, it is useful to teach children how to develop independent tasks according to the various tasks of the teacher. Helps to understand and correct the number and plot of material for problem solving.

Work on issues involves several stages. The first is to listen to the issue and read it independently. Work on the issue begins with mastering its content. To teach students

to listen to the text of a reading problem, to distinguish key elements of the condition from the beginning, when students are not yet reading skills. Once the students have acquired reading skills, each student should not only listen to the text of the issue, but also read it independently, in order to better understand the context of the issue. To do this, they may be asked to read the question aloud first and then to read aloud again. In expressive reading, it is important to distinguish between the numerical data and the elements that are important to solve.

Example: 4 boxes of blue and 5 boxes of red paper for labor lessons. How many packs of paper have you bought for work lessons?

When reading this issue read aloud the words "4 Blue Blue", "5 Pack Red" and "All". The text of the issue is read twice by the teacher or the students. However, it is important to gradually teach children to understand the meaning of the text once they have read it. To do this, it is important to ask guidance questions and assignments that will appeal to your students. First of all, the tasks are simple and then complex. The instructor should not only give a simple instruction to listen, but also give the students a specific additional task that is important to know. Example: "Listen carefully to the text of the issue and be prepared to repeat it." This is the simplest task. It can be used in the early stages of learning. The tasks will then be more complicated: "I'll tell you the problem right now," said the teacher. "Be prepared to tell what you know and what you need to know." In this case, students will be actively engaged in the process of listening to the text of the issue. M.I. According to Moro, students do their own sorting of the text

by separating the unknown from the unknown. As you listen to the text of the issue, students should understand the links between the amount and the amount sought, along with remembering the question and the question. Students will be able to solve the issue independently if the students are attentive and have the ability to read independently(Holt, 2010).

One of the most important skills is to distinguish what is unknown, what is important, and how to communicate with those who are involved in the matter. Without these skills, he / she cannot teach them to solve problems independently. At the initial introduction of the issue, students are introduced to the parts of the issue. Example: 7 boxes of plastic in one box contains more than 2 parts of plastic in the other box. How many pieces of plastic do both boxes contain? When the text is read, the teacher asks the students the following question: (In this case, students are instructed to listen to the issue before it is read.

- What is known about children? (In this case there are 7 bottles in one box and 2 lbs more in the other).
- What's the matter? (The condition of this issue).
- What is not known in this issue? (It is not known how many pieces of plastic there are in both boxes).
- What's the matter? (Question of the issue).

A brief note of the content of the issue will help the reader to understand and separate the numerical data based on their memory. At the same time, their compilation helps to understand what is given and what to look for. Summary of the issue.

- a) Complete demonstration
- b) Inadequate representation
- c) schematic
- d) in the form of tables
- (d) A brief note.

Short note of the above issue:

1st q - 7 lanes

2nd q -? More than 2 parts

The content of the issue can be illustrated by the picture. To do this, draw a picture of two plastic boxes. In the first box there are 7 plates, in the second box there are two and more than 2 plates. Conditional fixation of the problem, ie placing rectangular or incisors instead of plastic ones (Clark, Huxley, & Mountford, 2010).

1-q-□□□□□□□ } ?
2-q-□□□□□□□□

To illustrate the contents of a case using a drawing, each cell of the notebook is taken for one plate. The 7 boxes in the first box are illustrated with a 7-cell incision. In the second box, the plate is represented by a cross-section of the same length and another 2-in.

Short story content

1-q- }
2-q- } ?

A short note of issues can also be illustrated using a table.

Example: 12 kg of honey is poured into 4 jars How many kg of honey in 3 cans?

jar capacity	number of jars	all ban. capacity
the same	4 px	12 kg
	3 px	?

Depending on how the issue is handled, the shortest note types will be handy.

In the elementary grades, the mathematical teaching methodology manuals provide analytical and synthetic methods of problem analysis. Analytical analysis is the separation of known and unknown data, and synthetic analysis combines specific numbers to answer a question. The analytical method of the case analysis is a chain of reasoning that is at the very beginning of the chain. To find the answer to your question, you will select the necessary information that is not indicated or not. However, this information may be generated from other information. A synthetic method of case analysis is a judgment that refers to what one can learn from the data by combining the numerical data. and then merge with the newly created information. This merger will continue until the question is answered. There is only one operation where analysis is

continuous with sinter, so that a complex problem can be extended to simple issues (Put-van den Beemt & Smith, 2016).

Conclusion

However, this operation can be done in two ways: by going from unknown to unknown or from unknown. Thus, the problem analysis is performed by an analytical-synthetic method, because the solution of the problem must always be in the character that the researcher must go from the given data to the researcher and the search engine. After analyzing the issue, a solution plan is established, that is, to answer the final question, we first determine what we know and then what we know.

References

- Anonymous. (2010). UN tourism chief hails potential of Silk Road travel. *UzReport.Com*, n/a.
- Baxtishodovich, B., Suyunovich, T., News, A. K.-W. S., & 2017, undefined. (n.d.). The start-up of tourism in Central Asia Case of Uzbekistan. *Infona.Pl*. Retrieved from <https://www.infona.pl/resource/bwmeta1.element.psjd-b0bae11d-b866-4574-95a1-799eafccc3cd>
- Blasko, V., Electronics, V. K.-I. transactions on P., & 1997, undefined. (n.d.). A new mathematical model and control of a three-phase AC-DC voltage source converter. *Ieeexplore.Ieee.Org*. Retrieved from

<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/554176/>

Clark, G., Huxley, J., & Mountford, D. (2010). Organising local economic development.

Retrieved from [https://www.oecd-](https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/content/publication/9789264083530-en)

[ilibrary.org/content/publication/9789264083530-en](https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/content/publication/9789264083530-en)

Holt, E. (2010). Uzbekistan restricts foreign travel for doctors. *Lancet*.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)60790-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)60790-8)

Put-van den Beemt, W., & Smith, R. (2016). Smart tourism tools: linking technology to the touristic resources of a city. *Smart Tourism Congress Barcelona*, 1–12.

Retrieved from

https://www.cett.es/fixters/campushtml/MiniWebs/122/papers/PUT_SMITH.pdf

Razakov Sh, A., & Shakhgunova, Gs. (2001). [Current malaria situation in the Republic of Uzbekistan]. *Med Parazitol (Mosk)*, (1), 39–41. Retrieved from

<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11548313>

Turner, R., & Freiermuth, E. (2017). *Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2017: Portugal*.

World Travel & Tourism Council. Retrieved from <https://www.wttc.org/-/media/files/reports/economic-impact-research/countries-2017/portugal2017.pdf>

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